

Making Photocatalyst Screening Photo-Efficient – Geometric Radiation Field Model Assisted Design of a Direct Irradiation Module for the Multi-Batch Screening Reactor

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Abstract

Photochemical process development critically relies on efficient and reproducible parameter screening, which consequently requires irradiation modules capable of delivering high photon fluxes with well-defined and homogeneous light fields. However, state of the art indirect irradiation modules are inherently limited in achievable photon flux by optical losses during reflection onto the reactor surface. In this work, a model-assisted workflow for the design and optimization of a direct LED irradiation module is presented, specifically aiming at enhancing a multi-batch screening photoreactor. A computationally efficient geometric radiation field model was developed to rapidly predict spatial irradiance distributions and enable large-scale parameter screening across LED number, placement, and height. The model was validated against radiometric measurements and ray tracing simulations, achieving deviations below 11 % in mean irradiance and below 1 % in homogeneity for simple reflector-free arrangements, while reducing computation time by four orders of magnitude compared to ray tracing. Combining the geometric model with Monte-Carlo sampling and multi-objective Pareto optimization based on homogeneity and photon utilization enabled identification of near-optimal module height, LED number and spatial arrangement. Experimental validation demonstrated that the optimized direct irradiation module increased the mean irradiance by a factor of up to 8.2 compared to the existing indirect irradiation concept while using only 2.67 times more LEDs, alongside an improvement in homogeneity from approximately 0.67 to more than 0.80. The addition of diffuse reflectors further increased mean irradiance by up to 38 % and reduced the sensitivity to LED placement. The presented approach enables efficient, scalable irradiation module optimization and substantially improves the throughput and reliability of photochemical parameter screening.

Introduction

Light-driven catalytic reactions have received continuously growing attention over the past decade in the fields of sustainable energy conversion and synthetic chemistry.^[1] Efficient photocatalytic systems require the coordinated optimization of several interdependent parameters, including optical absorption properties, charge-carrier separation, catalytic activity, and surface reaction kinetics^[2,3] The reaction rate of many photochemical processes is limited by the absorbed photon flux, especially for those with quantum yields below 1. Almost no scientific publications exist in which the photochemical process is intensified to such an extent that other processes like mass transport become limiting. To improve photocatalytic systems and enhance overall activity, it is therefore required to quantify photons available in a photoreactor and consider photons as a reagent^[4,5]. Moreover, control over radiant intensity and temporal irradiation patterns represents an important degree of freedom, as temporal modulation of light fields can significantly influence photocatalytic performance^[6,7].

From an engineering perspective, irradiation must therefore be considered as both a control and screening parameter. Equipment for experimentally studying light-driven reactions, such as photochemical screening platforms, must consequently ensure both sufficiently high and spatially homogeneous irradiation across the entire screening surface to ensure comparable results across all screened reactors. Achieving homogeneous irradiation over large screening areas remains a central challenge in photocatalytic reactor design. Due to the dependence of the photocatalytic activity on the absorbed photon flux, uniform irradiation is a fundamental requirement for quantitative two-dimensional screening^[8-11]. Commercially available light emitting diodes (LED), the currently most frequently used type of light sources in laboratories, exhibit pronounced angle-dependent radiant intensity distributions that differ significantly between devices^[12-14]. To improve irradiation uniformity, concepts such as optimized spatial arrangement of light sources, the application of lenses with tailored optical properties, and the use of reflective materials have been proposed^[15-19]. Diffusely reflective materials such as PTFE are particularly suitable for reflector construction due to their high diffuse reflectivity^[20].

Recently, the multi-batch screening reactor was reported as an extension to the modular photoreactor platform^[21] enabling screening of up to 49 reactor vials and applied to photocatalytic hydrogen evolution investigations. The developed indirect irradiation module was installed on a roller shaker (IKA Roller Shaker 10 Digital), with a reactor surface of 330 mm × 340 mm available for screening. Indirect irradiation was realized by 6 LEDs and a curved diffuse PTFE reflector yielding high irradiation homogeneity of 66 % at the compromise of a

lower irradiation intensity corresponding, resulting in an irradiation efficiency of around 33.9 % – 34.7 %.^[22]

Indirect irradiation concepts employing diffuse reflectors have been demonstrated to provide homogeneous illumination, albeit often at the cost of reduced photon flux^[22]. In contrast, direct irradiation concepts enable higher intensities but require careful design to ensure appropriate overlap of the emitted radiation fields to yield a homogeneous irradiation of larger areas^[23,24]. Light-emitting diodes (LEDs) are particularly attractive for such applications due to their controllability and robustness^[25,26]. Nevertheless, the resulting radiation field is strongly affected by parameters such as LED type, number, spacing, and the distance between the light source and the screening surface^[27,28].

Radiometric measurements in combination with ray tracing simulations are frequently employed for the analysis and optimization of radiation fields^[29–37]. To quantitatively assess the radiation field, the power absorption efficiency ϕ , the homogeneity H , and the global illumination efficiency η defined in Eqs. (1)-(3) are commonly applied in literature^[24,29,37].

The power absorption efficiency ϕ describes the fraction of the emitted photons that are absorbed. It is defined as the ratio between the absorbed photon flux on the detection plane $q_{p,abs}$ to the total emitted photon flux of N LEDs, each with an individual emitted photon flux $q_{p,LED}$.

$$\phi = \frac{q_{p,abs}}{N \cdot q_{p,LED}} \quad (1)$$

The homogeneity H is calculated based on the mean irradiance E_{mean} and its standard deviation $std(E)$. This metric quantifies the uniformity of the irradiation field across the detection plane. A homogeneity value of unity corresponds to perfectly uniform irradiation, whereas decreasing values indicate increasing spatial inhomogeneity.

$$H = 1 - \frac{std(E)}{E_{mean}} \quad (2)$$

The global illumination efficiency η is defined as the product of power absorption efficiency and homogeneity. It simultaneously takes into account efficient photon utilization and uniform irradiance and has therefore been adopted in recent optimization studies^[29,37].

$$\eta = \phi H \quad (3)$$

Ray tracing allows for a realistic description of optical effects, including diffuse reflectivity and multiple scattering, but is computationally demanding and therefore not suited for screening a large number of different configurations. As a result, irradiation module development is often still based on empirical trial-and-error approaches, which are time-consuming, labor-intensive, and require substantial expertise in light-source emission characteristics

and optical material properties. These limitations highlight the need for fast and resource-efficient optimization strategies. In this context, geometrical radiation field modelling^[38] represents a promising basis to elaborate pre-screening workflows for selecting promising candidates, while ray tracing can subsequently be applied for verification of selected configurations.

Finally, additive manufacturing technologies such as 3D printing provide cost-efficient routes for the fabrication of customized reactor and irradiation components, enabling rapid prototyping and flexible photoreactor design.^[39–42]

Based on these aspects, this work develops and optimizes a direct irradiation module for the multi-batch screening photoreactor. The workflow combines expert-knowledge-driven empirical optimization with model-driven refinement. Empirical optimization serves as a reference for geometrical radiation field modeling, validated through ray tracing simulations and radiometric measurements.

Results and Discussion

Direct Irradiation Module Concept and Initial Design

Figure 1: **a** grid positioning to the 8 LED configuration after empirical optimization, **b** corresponding LED module with static reflector and **c** direct irradiation module in operation with green 530 nm LEDs.

To extend the screening capabilities of the multi-batch screening photoreactor, the development of a direct irradiation module as additional module for the multi-batch screening photoreactor (see Figure 1 **c**) was chosen as test case for the developed work flow, including the design, manufacturing and experimental testing of the module. To evaluate the established development workflow, the chosen geometrical constraints match the requirements of the multi-batch screening photoreactor and therefore irradiation intensity and homogeneity can be directly compared with the performance of the indirect irradiation module^[21].

Initial empirical optimization of the direct irradiation module was conducted with respect to the number of LEDs, relative lateral positioning of the LEDs mounted on the heat sink, the vertical distance between the LEDs and irradiated detector plane and the necessity of the deployment of additional reflectors to ensure both homogeneous and intense irradiation. This resulted in the use of 8 LEDs, to keep the parameter space in a reasonable dimension, arranged in a combined hexagonal and pentagonal pattern at a vertical distance (*z* distance) of 130 mm relative- to the detector plane. The LED pattern showing the best performance is depicted in Figure 1 **a** and **b** and was manufactured for experimental evaluation.

Spatially resolved irradiation intensity and homogeneity over the defined detector plane was evaluated for two LED types: a UV LED with a peak emission wavelength of 365 nm (optical power: 875 mW, current: 500 mA) and a green LED with a peak emission wavelength of 530 nm (optical power: 281 mW, current of 350 mA)^[43,44]. For the evaluation, two-dimensional radiometry was used based on the method proposed by Sender et al.^[45]. Detailed information on the conducted radiometric scans can be found in ESI section 1.

The mean irradiance of the indirect irradiation module was reported as 16.8 W m^{-2} (365 nm) and 4.6 W m^{-2} (530 nm) at the datasheet reference current of 500 mA and 350 mA, respectively^[21]. The corresponding homogeneities are 0.66 and 0.68 (see ESI section 4 for the

calculations). Switching to direct irradiation without reflectors led to a substantial improvement for both LED types. In the case of the 365 nm LEDs, the mean irradiance increased to 40.0 W m^{-2} , while homogeneity improved to 0.77. Similarly, for the 530 nm LEDs, the mean irradiance increased to 12.0 W m^{-2} with a homogeneity of 0.75.

The installation of diffuse rectangular PTFE reflector sheets at the outside of the heatsink further enhanced performance, since light that would otherwise bypass the detection plane is redirected to it. For the 365 nm LEDs, the mean irradiance increased to 44.1 W m^{-2} and homogeneity to 0.83, corresponding to an additional 10 % increase in mean irradiance relative to the reflector-free direct module. For the 530 nm LEDs, the reflector increased the mean irradiance to 14.7 W m^{-2} and the homogeneity to 0.80, representing an increase in mean irradiance of approximately 23 %.

Model-Assisted Optimization

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the geometric model approach to calculate the irradiance E at position (x, y) on an arbitrary detection plane geometry by superimposing the angle-dependent radiant intensity profiles $I(\theta)$ of N equal LEDs i at lateral coordinates (x_i, y_i) and height z_i .

Optimizing the irradiation module requires exploration of a large design space defined by the number of LEDs, their lateral positions, and the LED–reactor distance. Even at a fixed height, eight LEDs can theoretically be arranged in approximately 14 trillion different configurations on the 169 mounting positions. Variation in both LED count and height further increases the design space exponentially, making optimization by expert intuition or computationally demanding ray tracing simulation infeasible.

As a computationally cheap alternative, the geometric radiation field model illustrated in Figure 2 was developed. The model predicts the irradiance on the detection plane $E(x, y)$ by superimposing the angle-dependent radiant intensity profiles $I(\theta)$ of N equal LEDs i at lateral coordinates (x_i, y_i) and height z_i according to Eq. (4). A detailed derivation is provided in the section of Materials and Methods.

$$E(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{z_i}{(x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2)^{3/2}} I(\theta) \quad (4)$$

The prediction performance of the geometric radiation field model was evaluated against ray tracing simulations in Ansys Speos, and radiometric measurements using the reference LED arrangement shown in Figure 3 (a) without reflectors. Figure 3 (a)–(c) show the close agreement in magnitude and spatial distribution of the irradiance field obtained by the three methods using UV-LEDs, and Figure 3 (d) and (e) summarize the corresponding mean irradiance and homogeneity for both investigated LED types. The corresponding irradiance plots for the 530 nm LEDs are shown in ESI section

The geometric model reproduced both the magnitude and spatial distribution of the irradiance field with high accuracy. Deviations in mean irradiance relative to experimental

measurements remained below 11 %, comparable to the prediction accuracy of ray tracing for both LED types, while deviations in homogeneity were below 3 %. Calculation of a full spatial irradiance field required approximately 5 ms, compared to ~20 s for ray tracing, corresponding to a computational speed-up of four orders of magnitude. This efficiency enables systematic exploration of large design spaces that are otherwise computationally unfeasible. However, it is limited to simple geometries without reflecting parts, so that a consecutive detailed ray tracing study is required.

Figure 3: Comparison of simulations using the geometric model and ray tracing with radiometric measurements: a)-c) 2D irradiance distribution on the detection plane using eight 365 nm LEDs; d)-e) comparison of the calculated mean irradiance and homogeneity values to the indirect irradiation module for 365 nm LEDs and 530 nm LEDs. The LEDs were operated at the datasheet reference current of 500 mA and 350 mA, respectively.

In alignment with the geometrical properties of the best manual configuration shown in Figure 1, eight LEDs positioned at a fixed height of 13 cm were evaluated for each configuration as a first optimization step. To limit the search space to physically plausible LED

Figure 4: Pareto-optimization results for the two investigated LED-types including the configurations the best individual metrics and the configuration with the best objective score. A fixed number of 8 LEDs and 13 cm height are used as boundary conditions. The metrics for the indirect irradiation module are calculated based on <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3RE00398A>.

arrangements, the search space was restricted to point-symmetric configurations around the module center, with two LEDs in each quadrant, reducing the number of feasible arrangements from 14 trillion to approximately 500,000 (see ESI section 6). The irradiance was constrained to a maximum boundary $E_{\text{bound}} = 150 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ to prevent local over-irradiation.

Each configuration was assessed by the homogeneity H and the normalized mean irradiance $E_{\text{mean}}/E_{\text{bound}}$. The normalized mean irradiance was selected instead of the power absorption efficiency commonly used in the literature, as it enables a direct performance comparison between configurations with different numbers of LED.

To account for the inherent trade-off between these metrics, they were combined into the weighted objective function given in Eq. (5).

$$obj = t \cdot H + (1 - t) \cdot \frac{E_{\text{mean}}}{E_{\text{bound}}} \quad (5)$$

The weighting factor t determines the relative impact of homogeneity and mean irradiance on the objective value obj . Varying t between 0 and 1 resulted in the Pareto fronts shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** a) and b) for the 365 nm and 530 nm LEDs, respectively. For comparison, the performance indicators are also shown for the state-of-the-art indirect irradiation module, the best manual configuration, and the optimal configuration, identified by maximizing $H \cdot E_{\text{mean}}/E_{\text{bound}}$ comparable to the approach suggested by

Matiazzo et al. who used the similarly defined illumination efficiency described by Eq. (3) for radiation field optimization^[29].

The obtained boundary solutions for $t = 1$ and $t = 0$ are consistent with physical expectations. High homogeneity but low mean irradiance occurs when the LEDs are placed toward the outer regions of the detection plane, resulting in a more uniform irradiance distribution while a significant fraction of the emitted light bypasses the plane. Conversely, low homogeneity but high mean irradiance results when placing LEDs closer to the center, where overlapping intensity profiles create local irradiance peaks. Across both LED types, a “4×2” configuration with four radial positions of two LEDs provided the best overall compromise between homogeneity and mean irradiance. Compared to the state-of-the-art indirect irradiation module, the mean irradiance is increased by a factor of 2.1-2.7 and the homogeneity is increased from 0.66-0.68 to 0.82-0.83.

The optimal arrangement was independent of the LED type, indicating that differences in radiant intensity profiles have only minor influence on the determination of the ideal LED placement. Matiazzo et al. identified the LED viewing angle as a key parameter governing optimal positioning^[29]. Accordingly, the insensitivity of the optimal arrangement of the led type is consistent with the similar viewing angles of the UV and green LEDs of 130° and 120°, respectively^[43,44]. Additionally, the relatively large distance between the LEDs and the detector plane further reduces the impact of LED-specific angular emission characteristics.

The best manual configuration used for validation lies close to the Pareto front, confirming that it already represents a near-optimal compromise between homogeneity and mean irradiance. The results highlight the potential of model-based geometrical radiation field optimization, as optimal irradiation module configurations can be identified within seconds, compared to weeks for empirical optimization, without requiring prior expert knowledge.

While this first optimization isolates the effect of lateral LED placement, the practical module design additionally required optimization of LED number and height. Accordingly, the search space boundaries were expanded to $1 \leq N \leq 16$ LEDs and LED heights between 5 cm and 15 cm in 1 cm increments, reflecting technical constraints and experimentally relevant distances. All other optimization boundaries remained unchanged.

To manage the huge number of more than $1.24 \cdot 10^{23}$ theoretically feasible candidates, the Monte-Carlo sampling approach described in ESI chapter 6 was applied, generating 5 million configurations per LED type to achieve broad coverage of the design space. The resulting Pareto analysis is shown in Figure 5.

Configurations near the Pareto optimum achieved approximately a 2.5-fold increase in mean irradiance compared to the best manual configuration, while maintaining comparable

Figure 5: Pareto-optimization results for the two investigated LED-types and comparison to indirect irradiation and the manually optimized configuration. A variable number of 1-16 LEDs and 5-15 cm height are used as optimization boundary conditions. The three near-pareto optimal configurations UV1-3 and GRN1-3 are chosen for further investigation.

homogeneity. As expected for stochastic sampling in high-dimensional design spaces, these solutions represent near-optimal designs rather than guaranteed global optima. Nevertheless, the identified configurations align closely with published findings on optimal LED placement, where grid-like arrangements similar to the identified optimal configuration, denoted as C in Figure 5 (a) and (b), are reported as most effective^[24].

To evaluate the influence of reflectors and detailed optical interactions beyond the geometric model, the three most promising near-Pareto-optimal configurations each, UV1 – UV3 and GRN1-GRN3 in Figure 5, were further analyzed by ray tracing and radiometric measurements. The corresponding manufactured direct irradiation module is depicted in Figure 6 exemplarily for configuration GRN3. Figure 6 (a) – (c) shows the physical implementation of the direct irradiation module with mounted LEDs. Figure 6 (d) – (f) illustrate the height-adjustable reflector concept that enabled experimental radiometric measurements at reflector heights of 60 mm, 80 mm, and 90 mm. The modular reflector design is schematically shown in Figure 6 (f) and consists of stackable 3D-printed rectangular reflector elements with individual heights of 60 mm, 20 mm, and 10 mm, allowing flexible adjustment of the total reflector height. All reflector modules are lined with optical PTFE to achieve high and constant reflectivity within the UV and visible region, aligned with the used 365 nm and 530 nm LEDs.

Figure 6: Overview of the direct irradiation module used for radiometric measurements of configurations UV1-3 and GRN1-3. **a** grid positions of GRN3, **b** corresponding LED module **c** direct irradiation module in operation. **a** modular reflector equipped with 16 LEDs, **b** stacked modular reflector and **c** corresponding CAD model.

Figure 7 highlights the effect of reflectors on mean irradiance and homogeneity for the 365 nm LEDs. Similar studies for the green LEDs are summarized in section 7 ESI. Including reflectors increased the mean irradiance on the detection plane by 8 % – 38 % across all evaluated configurations, as the light that would otherwise bypass the plane is redirected. Upon addition of reflectors, the mean irradiance increased from configuration UV1 to UV3, while the corresponding decrease in homogeneity follows the same qualitative trend observed for the reflector-free module, but less pronounced. From a practical perspective, this indicates that the exact LED arrangement and height play a subordinate role once reflectors are used, provided that the LEDs are reasonably distributed across the module area.

Due to its simplicity, the geometric radiation field model cannot describe reflective components and was therefore not applied to configurations that include reflectors. Instead, ray tracing simulations were used as comparison to radiometric measurements. Despite the increased complexity of optical interactions, the ray tracing predictions remained in good agreement with radiometric measurements, with deviations in mean irradiance below 19 %, well within experimental uncertainty of radiometric measurements^[45] and accuracy of ray tracing simulations as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 7: Comparison of the mean irradiance and homogeneity of configurations UV1, UV2, and UV3 using 365 nm LEDs without and with reflectors according to the geometric model, ray tracing simulations, and radiometric measurements.

A quantitative comparison of the irradiation concepts is summarized in Figure 8. The indirect irradiation module achieved mean irradiances of 16.8 W m^{-2} (365 nm) and 4.6 W m^{-2} (530 nm) with homogeneities of 0.66 and 0.68, respectively, using six LEDs. Manual optimization of a direct irradiation module with eight LEDs increased the mean irradiance to 44.1 W m^{-2} (365 nm) and 14.7 W m^{-2} (530 nm), while improving homogeneity to 0.83 and 0.80. The model-based optimization further enhanced performance for configurations with up to 16 LEDs, yielding mean irradiances of 110.0 W m^{-2} at 365 nm and 34.5 W m^{-2} at 530 nm, alongside homogeneities of 0.81 and 0.82, respectively.

Compared to the indirect irradiation concept, this corresponds to an approximately 7-fold increase in mean irradiance at 365 nm and an 8.2-fold increase at 530 nm, while using only 2.7 times more LEDs. At the same time, irradiation homogeneity improved from values below 0.70 to higher than 0.80.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the model-assisted optimization workflow enables a substantial enhancement of photon delivery efficiency and irradiation uniformity compared to conventional indirect irradiation concepts. This renders the optimized direct irradiation

module particularly well suited for high-throughput and reproducible photochemical parameter screening.

Figure 8: Comparison of the mean irradiance and homogeneity of the literature-known indirect irradiation module (6 LEDs), the manually optimized direct irradiation module (8 LEDs arranged according to Figure 1a, 13 cm height, with reflectors), and the model-based optimized module (16 LEDs arranged according to C3 in Figure 5, 6 cm height, with reflectors) for 365 nm LEDs and 530 nm LEDs measured by radiometry. The LEDs were operated at the datasheet reference current of 500 mA and 350 mA, respectively.

Conclusion

This work presents a comprehensive direct irradiation module design strategy for the Multi-Batch Screening Reactor (MBSR) using a fast geometric radiation field model. The geometric model proved capable of predicting irradiance distributions with deviations below 11 % relative to radiometric measurements while offering a reduction in computation time of four orders of magnitude compared to conventional ray tracing. This efficiency combined with Monte-Carlo sampling enabled the exploration of a huge design space with $1.24 \cdot 10^{23}$ feasible candidates, including variations in LED count, height, and spatial arrangement.

The optimization studies demonstrated the trade-offs between mean irradiance and homogeneity, and the Pareto-front analysis provided a simple, visual framework to balance these conflicting objectives. The solutions identified as optimal are consistent with physical intuition and literature findings and were largely independent of LED type. Incorporating reflectors enhanced the irradiance by 16 % - 38 % due to secondary optical effects and reduced the sensitivity to LED placement.

The resulting direct irradiation module achieves a substantial performance enhancement compared to the state-of-the-art indirect irradiation. By screening 5 million LED arrangements with 1-16 LEDs and heights between 5 cm and 15 cm, LED arrangements were identified that increase the mean irradiance by a factor of up to 8.2 while improving homogeneity from about 67 % to values above 80 %. These gains directly translate into higher external photonic efficiencies, shorter reaction times, and improved reproducibility of parallel photochemical experiments in the MBSR.

Overall, the presented optimization workflow provides an effective and transferable methodology for the rational design of LED-based illumination systems. Its combination of computational efficiency, optical accuracy, and engineering robustness makes it applicable not only the MBSR but also to a broad range of other photochemical reactor platforms.

Materials and Methods

Reflector Module Development

Diffuse reflector panels were manufactured from self-adhesive optical PTFE sheets (OPF200.XXX.300-U-K, BERGHOF Fluoroplastics) with a thickness of 2 mm^[46]. 3D-printed components, fabricated via Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) using black Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) filament, were used as structural support for the PTFE sheets to enable mounting at a defined relative positioning to the LEDs. A heat sink assembly features a 400 mm × 400 mm anodized aluminum plate onto which LEDs are mounted via screws with a center-to-center spacing of 25 mm. The aluminum plate is mounted to four 200 mm × 200 mm heat sinks (RS PRO, 903-3090) to ensure sufficient heat transfer during LED operation. Detailed information on the used reflector concepts is supplied in section 2 ESI. CAD models of the deployed heat sinks and 3D printed components are supplied in the corresponding GitHub repository <https://github.com/photonZfeed/modularPhotoreactor>.

Two different reflector modules were deployed in the conducted studies:

- I. a reflector module that can be coupled to a roller shaker (IKA Roller Shaker 10 Digital) as extension of the multi-batch screening photoreactor with fixed reflector height, and;
- II. a height-adjustable, modular reflector used for validation of the model-based radiation field optimization at varying distance between LEDs and detection plane.

Reflector with Fixed Height

The fixed-height reflector (see Figure 1) module consists of four walls, two measuring 330 mm and two measuring 350 mm in length, with a height of 100 mm. These reflectors are constructed from red Plexiglass and lined with a 2 mm thick PTFE sheet. Structural integrity and reproducible assembly are secured by 3D printed components. A 25 mm gap separates the heat sink from the reflector walls from the top, providing sufficient airflow for convective cooling and preventing thermal buildup.

Modular Reflector with Adjustable Height

The modular reflector assembly consisted of three individual components manufactured by 3D printing. Each component comprised rectangular panels with lengths of 330 mm and 350 mm, lined with PTFE sheets, and heights of 60 mm, 20 mm, and 10 mm, respectively. This design yielded three rectangular reflector modules that could be stacked to obtain total reflector heights of 60 mm, 80 mm, and 90 mm, which were used for the 2D radiometric measurements (see Figure 7). All inner surfaces were lined with PTFE sheets providing diffuse, Lambertian reflectance in the UV and visible spectral range. The reflector modules were placed directly onto the LED-mounted heat sink without clearance, and the bottom plane of

the reflector in contact with the heat sink was defined as the optical reference plane for all z-distance definitions. Relative positioning of the reflector modules with respect to the heat sink was ensured by 3D-printed corner alignment holders, preventing lateral displacement during measurements and ensuring reproducible stacking.

Radiometry

Radiometric measurements were performed using the 2D radiometry procedure described by Sender et al.^[45] to characterize the spatial irradiance distribution of UV and visible LED modules. Two LED types were investigated: a UV LED with a peak emission wavelength of 365 nm (model LST1-01G01-UV04-00, Lot 18107) and a green LED with a peak emission wavelength of 530 nm (model LST1-01F06-GRN1-00, Lot 19231).

For each LED type, measurements were performed at fixed operating conditions optimized for the used spectrometer detector. The UV LEDs were operated at a constant current of 500 mA using an integration time of 2.88 ms, whereas the green LEDs were operated at 350 mA with an integration time of 15.78 ms.

Radiometric scans were carried out for different LED configurations comprising a total of 16 LEDs, evaluated both with and without reflector utilization. For module preparation, two LED rows per wavelength were assembled, each consisting of 2×8 LEDs connected in series. The LED rows were operated at constant current using two programmable DC power supplies (Korad Lab KA3005P).

Measurements were performed at three defined vertical z-distances, measured from the LED mounting plane to the cosine corrector of the spectrometer. Based on geometric radiation field modelling, optimal distances of 6 cm, 8 cm, and 9 cm were selected. To prevent mechanical collision between the spectrometer (cosine corrector) and the irradiation module, all 2D radiometric scans were performed with an additional safety offset of 1 cm, resulting in effective measurement distances of 7 cm, 9 cm, and 10 cm, respectively.

For data evaluation spectral data were trimmed to the relevant emission regions of the respective LEDs prior to analysis: 300 nm – 450 nm for the UV LEDs and 450 nm – 600 nm for the green LEDs. Based on datasheet values^[43,44] for the current-dependent photon flux, the photon fluxes obtained by 2D radiometry were corrected using the measurements acquired at an effective distance of 7 cm for the respective LED modules operated under direct irradiation without reflector. The derived correction factors were subsequently applied to all measurements recorded at the corresponding z-distances, both for configurations without and with reflector.

Geometric Model Derivation

First, the angular emission of each LED is calculated based on manufacturer-provided relative radiant-intensity profiles $I_{\text{rel}}(\theta)$ and the optical power P_{LED} . θ represents the polar emission angle with respect to the optical axis. The absolute radiant-intensity distributions $I(\theta)$ is obtained by scaling the relative data according to Eq. (6) so that the surface integral of $I(\theta)$ corresponds to P_{LED} . For this purpose, a rotationally symmetrical emission profile is assumed.

$$I(\theta) = \frac{P_{\text{LED}}}{2\pi \int_0^{\pi/2} I_{\text{rel}}(\theta) \sin \theta d\theta} I_{\text{rel}}(\theta) \quad (6)$$

Based on lateral coordinates of each LED, (x_i, y_i) , and the height z_i above the detection plane, the emission radius r , the emission angle θ , and irradiance contribution of the LED i , $E_i(x, y)$, are calculated based on Eqs. (7)-(9) which have been derived by Moreno et al.^[47].

$$r = \sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{x_i^2 + y_i^2}}{z_i}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$E_i(x, y) = \frac{I(\theta) \cos \theta}{r^2} = \frac{z_i}{(x_i^2 + y_i^2 + z_i^2)^{3/2}} I(\theta) \quad (9)$$

For the configuration of N LEDs, the total irradiance $E(x, y)$ is the linear superposition of the individual contributions.

$$E(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N E_i(x, y) \quad (10)$$

Eqs. (6)-(10) were implemented in Python 3.13.3. The full implementation is available at https://gitlab.uni-ulm.de/ag-ziegenbalg/direct_irradiation_module_optimization. All simulations were performed with a spatial resolution of 0.5 cm in x - and y -direction.

Ray Tracing in Ansys Speos

To assess the influence of incorporating optical reflectors into the lighting module, numerical simulations were conducted using the commercial ray tracing software Ansys Speos 2025 R2. The Speos solver employs a non-sequential ray tracing algorithm based on the Monte Carlo method to model detailed interactions of light with distinct materials^[30].

All simulations followed an identical workflow to ensure reproducibility. The three-dimensional geometry of the lighting module – including LEDs emitting surfaces and reflectors

(when applicable) - was created directly within the Speos CAD environment. Geometry creation was performed using a global Cartesian coordinate system, which served as the reference frame for the definition, positioning, and orientation of all optical components. The sensor plane was positioned in the xz-plane at $y=0$ and served as reference frame for the positioning of LEDs and reflectors. The emitting surfaces of the LEDs were defined as planar surfaces lying in the xz-plane, while the primary optical axis of the system was aligned with the positive y-direction.

The relative positions and orientations of the LEDs, reflectors, and detection plane were explicitly defined within this reference frame for each simulated configuration. The surrounding domain was assumed to be homogeneous and filled with air, modeled as a non-absorbing, non-scattering medium with a refractive index of 1.0.

Surface sources were created to represent both green and UV LEDs, with the following information: (i) LEDs surface area (Green: $d=2.15$ mm, UV: $d=2.6$ mm); (ii) power emitted by each LED (Green: 0.28 W, UV: 0.875 W); (iii) light spectrum (Green: 530 nm peak with 30 nm half width, UV: 365 nm peak with 5 nm half width); and (iv) light intensity distribution, which was provided by the manufacturer.

Simulations were performed with and without the presence of reflectors. The reflector surfaces were modeled as purely reflective, incorporating mixed Lambertian–specular behavior that varies with the incident angle. The specular–Lambertian fractions were defined following the angle-dependent optical properties reported by Janecek and Moses (2008)^[48], summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Optical properties applied to the reflection in the reflector material.

Incident Angle (°)	0	2	6	10	14	18	22	26	30	34	38	42	50	70	80	90
Specular (%)	35.0	25.7	1.0	10.0	9.0	14.6	17.1	30.1	68.8	99.0	99.0	99.7	100	100	100	100
Lambertian (%)	65.0	74.3	99.0	90.0	91.0	85.4	82.9	69.9	31.2	1.0	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Irradiance was quantified using a radiance sensor of 33 cm × 34 cm positioned at several LEDs-to-sensor distances. The sensor surface was discretized using a triangular mesh with a mesh step equivalent to 1 mm, resulting in a mesh with 225,576 nodes, where irradiance values are calculated. A planar integration, orthogonal to the sensor plane, was performed, considering the cosine fall off of the irradiance as a function of the incident angle, in accordance with Eq. (9).

The propagation of rays from sources to sensor was tracked via a Direct Simulation. Double precision was enabled for the ray tracer, and the maximum number of interactions was kept at 100, which means that a single ray can interact with the geometry at a maximum of 100 times before its propagation stops. The stop criterion for the simulations was set as 1.6×10^7 rays, defined after a ray number sensitivity test described in the supporting information.

Acknowledgements

This publication was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft DFG as part of the collaborative research center TRR234 "CataLight" (364549901), project C6. This study also received support from "Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico – CNPq" (processes 305472/2025-9 – C.S. and 312247/2022-2 – N.P.) and "Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Estado de Santa Catarina (FAPESC), process 985/2025 (T.M.).

Authors Contributions

- Please list according to CRediT
 - <https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/credit.html>

Benedikt Wiedemann: - conceptualization (equal) - data curation (lead), formal analysis (lead), investigation (equal), - methodology (equal) - software (lead) - validation (equal) - visualization (equal), writing – original draft (equal), and writing – review & editing (equal).

Daniel Kowalczyk: - conceptualization (equal) - data curation (supporting), formal analysis (supporting), investigation (equal), – validation (equal) - visualization (equal), writing – original draft (equal), and writing – review & editing (equal).

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Sources

- Aim for around 50 sources per manuscript

- [1] T. H. Rehm, *Chem. - A Eur. J.* **2020**, *26*, 16952–16974.
- [2] M. de L. M. Ballari, M. L. Satuf, O. M. Alfano, *Top. Curr. Chem.* **2019**, *377*, 22.
- [3] K. Takanabe, *ACS Catal.* **2017**, *7*, 8006–8022.
- [4] L. Buglioni, F. Raymenants, A. Slattery, S. D. A. Zondag, T. Noël, *Chem. Rev.* **2022**, *122*, 2752–2906.
- [5] H. E. Bonfield, T. Knauber, F. Lévesque, E. G. Moschetta, F. Susanne, L. J. Edwards, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11*, 804.
- [6] M. Sender, F. L. Huber, M. C. G. Moersch, D. Kowalczyk, J. Hniopek, S. Klingler, M. Schmitt, S. Kaufhold, K. Siewerth, J. Popp, B. Mizaikoff, D. Ziegenbalg, S. Rau, *ChemSusChem* **2022**, *15*, DOI 10.1002/cssc.202200708.
- [7] J. J. Devery, J. J. Douglas, J. D. Nguyen, K. P. Cole, R. A. Flowers, C. R. J. Stephenson, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 537–541.
- [8] Y. Ding, P. F. Gu, Z. R. Zheng, *Japanese J. Appl. Physics, Part 1 Regul. Pap. Short Notes Rev. Pap.* **2007**, *46*, 7771–7773.
- [9] F. R. Fournier, W. J. Cassarly, J. P. Rolland, in *Nonimaging Opt. Effic. Des. Illum. Sol. Conc. VI* (Eds.: R. Winston, J.M. Gordon), **2009**, p. 742302.
- [10] J. Z. Bloh, *Front. Chem.* **2019**, *7*, 128.
- [11] A. Enesca, *Catalysts* **2021**, *11*, 556.
- [12] M. Sender, D. Ziegenbalg, *Chemie Ing. Tech.* **2017**, *89*, 1159–1173.
- [13] J. Chen, S. Loeb, J. H. Kim, *Environ. Sci. Water Res. Technol.* **2017**, *3*, 188–202.
- [14] P. Fredes, U. Raff, E. Gramsch, M. Tarkowski, *J. Res. Natl. Inst. Stand. Technol.* **2021**, *126*, 1–25.
- [15] J. Tan, K. Yang, M. Xia, Y. Yang, *Opt. Appl.* **2011**, *41*, 507–517.
- [16] C. D' Alessandro, D. De Maio, T. Mundo, M. Musto, F. Di Giamberardino, M. Monti, D. Dalena, V. G. Palmieri, D. De Luca, E. Di Gennaro, R. Russo, *Sol. Energy* **2021**, *221*, 140–147.
- [17] A. J. W. Whang, S. M. Chao, C. N. Chen, Y. Y. Chen, H. C. Hsiao, X. D. Hu, *Opt. Rev.* **2011**, *18*, 218–223.
- [18] R. Wu, H. Wang, P. Liu, Y. Zhang, Z. Zheng, H. Li, X. Liu, *Opt. Commun.* **2013**, *300*, 100–107.

- [19] E. Chen, R. Wu, *Opt. Eng.* **2015**, *54*, 065103.
- [20] M. Janecek, W. W. Moses, *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.* **2008**, *55*, 2432-2437.
- [21] D. Kowalczyk, P. Li, A. Abbas, J. Eichhorn, P. Buday, M. Heiland, A. Pannwitz, F. H. Schacher, W. Weigand, C. Streb, D. Ziegenbalg, *ChemPhotoChem* **2022**, *6*, DOI 10.1002/cptc.202200044.
- [22] D. Kowalczyk, G. Knorr, K. Peneva, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2023**.
- [23] C. Reddick, C. Casado, K. Reynolds, S. Stanley, C. Pablos, J. Marugán, *Heliyon* **2023**, *9*, DOI 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16557.
- [24] D. J. Walsh, T. N. Schneider, B. D. Olsen, K. F. Jensen, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2023**, *8*, 416-423.
- [25] G. Di, Z. Zhu, Q. Dai, H. Zhang, X. Shen, Y. Qiu, Y. Huang, J. Yu, D. Yin, S. Küppers, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2020**, *379*, 122296.
- [26] D. Kowalczyk, P. Li, A. Abbas, J. Eichhorn, P. Buday, M. Heiland, A. Pannwitz, F. H. Schacher, W. Weigand, C. Streb, D. Ziegenbalg, *ChemPhotoChem* **2022**, *6*, e202200044.
- [27] T. I. Wong, X. Zhou, *Photonics* **2024**, *11*, 394.
- [28] S. M. Miranda, T. Matiazzo, N. Padoin, C. Soares, T. F. C. V Silva, V. J. P. Vilar, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2024**, *497*, 154705.
- [29] T. Matiazzo, V. J. P. Vilar, N. Padoin, C. Soares, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2024**, *285*, 119576.
- [30] T. Matiazzo, K. Ramaswamy, V. J. P. Vilar, N. Padoin, C. Soares, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2022**, *429*, 131670.
- [31] E. Müller-Erlwein, *Chemische Reaktionstechnik*, Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, Wiesbaden, **2015**.
- [32] M. Sender, B. Wriedt, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *6*, 1601-1613.
- [33] M. Sender, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, *6*, 1614-1627.
- [34] D. Kowalczyk, G. Knorr, K. Peneva, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2023**, *8*, 2967-2983.
- [35] J. Roegiers, J. van Walsem, S. Denys, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2018**, DOI 10.1016/J.CEJ.2018.01.047.
- [36] M. Á. Mueses, F. Machuca-Martínez, A. Hernández-Ramírez, G. L. Puma, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2015**, DOI 10.1016/J.CEJ.2015.05.056.
- [37] A. L. L. Zazueta, H. Destailats, G. L. Puma, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2013**, DOI 10.1016/J.CEJ.2012.11.085.
- [38] I. Moreno, M. Avendaño-Alejo, R. I. Tzonchev, *Appl. Opt.* **2006**, *45*, 2265-2272.

- [39] N. Jones, *Nature* **2012**, 487, 22-23.
- [40] M. D. Symes, P. J. Kitson, J. Yan, C. J. Richmond, G. J. T. Cooper, R. W. Bowman, T. Vilbrandt, L. Cronin, *Nat. Chem.* **2012**, 4, 349-354.
- [41] S. Rossi, A. Puglisi, M. Benaglia, *ChemCatChem* **2018**, 10, 1512-1525.
- [42] F. Guba, Ü. Tastan, K. Gugeler, M. Buntrock, T. Rommel, D. Ziegenbalg, *Chemie-Ingenieur-Technik* **2019**, 91, 17-29.
- [43] LUMINUS, “SST-10-UV Product Datasheet,” https://led-tech-shop.s3.eu-central-1.amazonaws.com/files/208/Luminus_SST-10-UV_Datasheet.pdf, **2023**.
- [44] New-EnergyLLC, “OSRAM Horticulture Starboards Industry Leading High Powered LED Starboards,” https://www.mouser.de/datasheet/3/1525/1/NewEnergy_StarBoard_Horticulture_Osram_DataSheet.pdf, **2025**.
- [45] M. Sender, B. Wriedt, D. Ziegenbalg, *React. Chem. Eng.* **2021**, 6, 1601-1613.
- [46] berghof Fluoroplastics, “Films made from Optopolymer,” <https://www.berghof-fluoroplastics.com/en/products/optopolymerr-optical-materials-and-coatings/films>, **2026**.
- [47] I. Moreno, C.-C. Sun, *Opt. Express* **2008**, 16, 1808-1819.
- [48] M. Janecek, W. W. Moses, *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.* **2008**, 55, 2443-2449.